

Status of Limited Incompatibilities and Completely Incompatibilities in Turkish Law

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To cite this article: Collaborate, Current Science, Volume 5, No. 5-10, 2024, p. 01– 13. - 0099-0001-2408-0501.

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("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ISSN: 2667-9515

Barcode: 977266795001

Editors Group:

Concessionaire: Tsisana Kharabadze

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Abstract

Article 8 and subsequent sections of the TMK address the law of individuals. The provisions generally control the determination of legal ability and legal competence. A person with legal

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ability may obtain rights and incur obligations. Our legislation stipulates that individuals who have attained the age of majority possess legal competence. A person devoid of judgment is deemed entirely disabled. Nonetheless, if an individual has discernment but is not an adult or is otherwise constrained, it is noted that they exhibit limited incapacity. Our legislation stipulates that the permission of a legal representative is necessary for the validity of legal transactions conducted by individuals with limited capacity.

Keywords: *Status Of Limited Incompatibilities, Completely Incompatibilities, Turkish Law, Law, Incompatibilities*

INTRODUCTION

The lawmaker has said that some incompetent persons may do certain transactions without the approval of their legal representatives. Individuals with limited capacity may engage in transactions or acquire benefits that are exclusively related to themselves¹. Our legislation stipulates that persons with limited capacity shall be held accountable for torts arising from the exercise of rights intrinsically linked to the person, as they possess the ability to perceive.² The legislator grants individuals with limited capacity the same legal protection as those with full capacity, as stipulated in TMK Article 16/I, allowing them to exercise their rights without requiring consent from their legal representatives in legal transactions³.

Regarding Minors with Discernment Power

¹ Sahin Mustafa; Switzerland Engagement Capacity of Minors and Persons with Limited Discernment Power (Limited Incompetent Persons) in Turkish Law within the Framework of Amendments Made to the Civil Code (TMK Art. 16/I, 118/II), 2020, Dergipark , p.9

² OĞUZMAN / SELICI / OKTAY OZDEMİR, p. 96;

³ AKİPEK / AKINTÜRK / ATEŞ KARAMAN, p. 325

Under the Turkish Law of Obligations, the principal stipulation is that an individual must possess the capacity for discernment while exercising their rights or discharging their obligations⁴. Consequently, those without competence and judgment will not be held accountable for their transactions. Transactions conducted by adolescents possessing discernment will be deemed legitimate contingent upon the approval provided by their legal representation. Given existing instances, I believe that a minor's involvement in a transaction requires permission and must be approved by a legal representation.⁵

Transactions That Can Be Done Alone

Free Gain

Upon analyzing the transactions permissible for those with limited capacity, those conducted without deliberation take precedence. Consequently, these transactions provide advantages for the individual with restricted capacity and do not anticipate any reciprocal responsibility⁶.

Instances of such agreements include a forgiveness agreement benefiting the party, a debt relief agreement, and a guarantee and surety arrangement that anticipates the security of a receivable.

Transactions Relating to Free Goods

Individuals without restricted ability may also engage in transactions using free assets. For instance: The assets allocated to the discretion of the individual under guardianship, The allocated portion of the kid excluded from the authority of the mother and father by a testamentary arrangement, The child's personal income⁷.

⁴ HATEMI, Hüseyin / KALKAN OĞUZTÜRK, Burcu: Family Law, Vedat Bookstore, Volume 4, Istanbul 2014, p. 13

⁵ KÖPRÜLÜ, Bülent: Civil Law p. 228

⁶ Ayan, Mehmet/ Ayan, Nurşen: Personal Law, Adalet Publishing House, B.9, Ankara, 2020, p.71

⁷ Ayan/ Ayan, p. 73

Transactions Regarding the Exercise of Rights Strictly Attached to the Person

Unlimited incapacitated individuals may engage in various activities, whereas limited incapacitated individuals may execute requests for name changes and transactions absolutely requiring a form, such as those pertaining to death dispositions.⁸ The limited incapacitated individual doing these transactions is not required to get consent from the legal representative or guardian. Nonetheless, some trades are restricted by legislation. Instances of these transactions include the adultification of a 15-year-old female and involvement by an incapacitated individual, among others. In these transactions, the legislator mandates the consent of the guardian or custodial parent, and the legitimacy of the transactions is contingent upon their approval.

Transactions Conducted as a Representative

They may execute transactions that incur debt for individuals with limited ability as their legal agents. Individuals with limited ability must enter into contracts or incur debts originating from responsibilities with the consent of their legal representatives. Certain transactions may only be executed with the consent of both the guardian and the parent. The parent may authorize transactions that incur debt for the child without limitation, save for those explicitly forbidden by law. A legal transaction between the kid and a third party, intended for the benefit of the child and the mother or father, requires the consent of the trustee or the court for the child to incur debt. Guardians need the authorization of the judge of the peace for certain transactions delineated by the legislature⁹.

⁸Ayan, Mehmet / Ayan, Nurşen, Introduction to Civil Law, Adalet Publishing House, B.12 Ankara, 2016, p.109

⁹Ayan/Ayan, p. 75

Transactions That Cannot Be Performed by Persons with Limited Licenses

The lawmaker has forbidden certain transactions for those with restricted ability. The restrictions are enumerated in TMK 439 as follows: The lawmaker has forbidden acting as a guarantor for those under guardianship, creating a foundation, or making substantial gifts. Transactions prohibited by the legal representative are cited as grounds for nullity in our legislation and are also seen as an abuse of rights.

Complete Incompetence

The Concept of Total Incapacity and the Legal Status of Total Incapacity Persons

Article 14 of the Turkish Civil Code stipulates that juveniles and those with disabilities lacking discernment are devoid of legal ability to act. The pertinent legal article indicates that discernment is impeded when an individual fails to comprehend the implications and motivations behind their acts or wants, leading to incongruent behavior. Our legislation designates those without the capacity for judgment as “completely incapacitated.” The incapacity of individuals, whether they are unrestricted or mature, is irrelevant owing to their lack of discernment. In other words, even if the utterly disabled are neither mature nor restricted¹⁰, These circumstances do not impact the disabled individuals. Individuals who are entirely disabled lack the ability to act and, therefore, do not possess the elements that compose their capacity for action. Individuals without the ability to act cannot engage in transactions that impact their assets and obligations, and they should not be held liable for harm inflicted upon others¹¹. Recent Supreme Court rulings suggest that individuals without insight may nevertheless be held accountable for their genuine harmful interactions with other parties. Transactions conducted by those without the capacity for judgment are also null and invalid. Some academics contend that the invalidity of transactions is retroactive, rendering them void

¹⁰ VELİDEDEOĞLU, Hıfzı Veldet , Turkish Civil Law (Personal Law), p.60

¹¹ AKİPEK, Jale /KARAMAN, Derya: Turkish Civil Law (Introduction Provisions, Personal Law), Volume I , 10th Edition, Istanbul 2013, p. 303

ab initio, which therefore affects the entirely incapable, so making the annulment outcome more fair¹².

Article 15 of the Turkish Civil Code states that the phrase “without prejudice to the situations in the law” signifies the existence of exceptions to the relevant article. In such situations, transactions executed by wholly incompetent individuals may only be annulled by a court ruling, so retaining the same terms and effects until rendered invalid. The following items may be enumerated as such;

- In the case of marriage of people who are completely incapacitated, the marriage is valid until the result of the annulment case, and children born during this period are considered to have been born in wedlock.

Heirs or testamentary beneficiaries may request the cancellation of the ÖBT made by those who are completely incapacitated .

- People who do not have the ability to discern due to illness or infancy are liable to bona fide third parties. In addition, according to one view in the doctrine, people who do not have the ability to discern can also use the rights that are strictly attached to the person ¹³.

Sanctions in Case of Violation of Article 15 of the Civil Code

Article 15 of the Turkish Civil Code stipulates that actions performed by individuals without the capacity for judgment have no legal repercussions. The interpretation of this legal article has been a topic of contention. According to the first perspective, it is invalidity, while the second perspective posits it as cancelability. Consequently, under the perspective that endorses the sanction of invalidity, the category of invalidity that excludes transactions considered essential by law for existence or validity is termed nullity. The transaction is deemed null and

¹² Akipek /Karaman, pp. 308-309

¹³ Akipek /Karaman, p. 316.

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void owing to the absence of requisite legal aspects, rendering it invalid because of the lack of validity components or their complete absence.¹⁴ Jurists espousing this perspective assert that the transaction in question cannot provide a conclusion or verdict due to its incompleteness or nonexistence from the outset. Proponents of the cancelability perspective contend that when legal penalties are imposed, the legal transaction persists despite its defects. Consequently, if the impairment is not asserted or a certain duration elapses, it will become effective, so acquiring the status of a legitimate transaction¹⁵. In conclusion, proponents of the classical perspective assert that a transaction executed by an individual without the capacity for discernment would be deemed unlawful, since it cannot attain legality even with the assent of a legal representation¹⁶. Proponents of the contemporary perspective also critique the classical viewpoint, asserting that the invalidity punishment will directly influence the outcome of the legal transaction. Upon separate examination of the legal transaction, it becomes evident that the notion of invalidity impacting certain provisions is not recognized and exerts no influence within the context of the material event; consequently, it does not hinder the primary and secondary provisions from yielding effects and determinations in the arising circumstances¹⁷. Consequently, jurists who embrace the contemporary perspective reject the notion of being subjected to the penalty of total invalidity¹⁸. Proponents assert that Article 15 of the TMK safeguards those without the capacity for judgment. The actions perpetrated by these individuals are subject to the punishment of total invalidity. The opposite opinion asserts that the transaction is susceptible to cancellation sanctions¹⁹.

Sample Jurisprudence Text

¹⁴ GÜRAL, p. 32; SAYMEN, Ferit H./ ELBİR: Turkish Law of Obligations, p. 32.

¹⁵ GÜRAL, p. 32; SAYMEN, Ferit H./ ELBİR: Turkish Law of Obligations, p. 107.

¹⁶ ÖZTAN, Bilge: Basic Concepts of Civil Law, 24th Edition, Ankara 2006, p.258

¹⁷ GÜRAL, p. 93.

¹⁸ Yücer İpek, Evaluation of TMK Art. 15 within the Framework of Application, Journal of the Union of Turkish Bar Associations, 2014, p.4

¹⁹ Akipek /Karaman, p. 309

3rd Civil Chamber 2020/5053 E., 2021/3106 K.

"Text of Jurisprudence"

COURT:CONSUMER COURT

Consequent to the adverse determination case between the parties, the court reviewed the defendant's attorney's timely appeal of the decision to accept the case; following the acceptance of the appeal petition, all documents in the file were examined and their merits assessed: The plaintiff's guardian; The plaintiff's father ...'s Aliaga Civil Court of First Instance's case numbered 2007/366, 2009/382, and the Forensic Medicine Report obtained determined that his perception and decision mechanisms did not work normally, and subsequently, with the same justification, he was restricted and appointed as his guardian by the Aliaga Civil Court of Peace's case numbered 2008/592, 2009/90, and that third parties outside the case deceived the restricted person and ensured that two loan agreements were signed with the defendant bank in an irregular manner, that the restricted person signed one of these loan agreements as a guarantor and the other as the principal debtor, that the defendant bank initiated enforcement proceedings based on the loan agreements due to non-payment of the debt, and that the loan agreements were invalid, and that the individual loan agreements dated 04.07.2007 and 18.06.2007 were cancelled, and that the plaintiff was not a debtor in the files numbered 2008/2786 and 2008/1885 of the Aliaga Enforcement Office. It was proposed that compensation for enforcement rejection be given against the defendant at a rate of 40% of the receivable.

The defendant sought the case's dismissal.

The court resolved to accept the case, annul the contracts dated 18/06/2007 and 04/07/2007 between the parties, establish that the plaintiff is not indebted to the defendant under these contracts according to files numbered 2008/2786 and 2008/1885 of the Aliaga Enforcement Office, and conclude that an assessment of bad faith compensation is unnecessary; the defendant subsequently appealed the ruling.

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The defendant's annulment of the loan agreements dated June 18, 2007, and July 4, 2007, which are the focus of the litigation, and the plaintiff's

In the examination of the appeal objections regarding the request of the Aliğa Enforcement Office to determine that there is no debt within the scope of the file numbered 2008/2786, which was initiated based on the loan agreement dated 18.06.2007; The plaintiff's guardian, with the guidance of third parties outside the case and the case at hand, requested that the restricted person signed two individual loan agreements with the defendant bank, one as the principal debtor and the other as the guarantor, and that the plaintiff did not have the ability to distinguish at the time the agreements were made, and requested that the loan agreements dated 18.06.2007 and 04.07.2006 be cancelled and that the plaintiff was not a debtor in terms of the enforcement proceedings initiated based on these agreements; The court ruled that, considering the report of the Forensic Medicine Institution in the file, the restricted person did not have the capacity to act on the date of the agreement, therefore the plaintiff has no liability arising from the enforcement proceedings initiated in terms of the agreements made with the defendant bank, and that the defendant bank neglected its duty of intelligence while providing the loan and did not investigate whether the borrower was subject to restriction and enforcement proceedings, and the lawsuit be accepted and the agreements dated 18.06.2007 and 04.07.2007 between the parties be cancelled.

The court determined that the plaintiff owed no obligation to the defendant according to the records numbers 2008/2786 and 2008/1885 from the Aliğa Enforcement Office.

The dispute is centered on whether the plaintiff is liable for the consumer credit he received after being seized pursuant to the contract he made with the defendant bank.

Article 15 of the Turkish Civil Code stipulates that, excluding special circumstances outlined in the legislation, the acts of an individual who lacks discernment are devoid of legal effect. Generally, the legal transactions of those deemed entirely incompetent are null and invalid. Nonetheless, exceptions to this norm exist. The concept of honesty and non-abuse of rights, as delineated in Article 2 of the TMK, is one such principle. Consequently, all individuals are

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required to adhere to the principle of honesty when exercising their rights and executing their duties. The legal framework does not safeguard the manifest misuse of a right. Prior to evaluating Article 15 in relation to Article 2 of the TMK, it is beneficial to elucidate the true intent behind the creation of this provision as indicated in Article 1/1 of the same legislation. The law deems legal transactions conducted by wholly incompetent individuals as illegitimate, with the intention of safeguarding these individuals from engaging in transactions detrimental to their interests and preventing their abuse by other parties. When this threat is removed and an individual of average intellect behaves similarly, asserting the illegality of the legal transaction would be an abuse of rights, which the law does not safeguard. According to the Unification of Jurisprudence of the Court of Cassation decision numbered 22/2 dated 09.03.1955, if an individual lacking discernment possessed the capacity for discretion, they would have behaved similarly; thus, a person of average intelligence should not assert the invalidity of the transaction on the grounds of incompetence. In the current instance, it is acknowledged that the plaintiff lacked the ability to act on the day the contract was executed. Conversely, he availed himself of bank loans, a privilege not usually accessible even to completely competent individuals in our nation, and derived an advantage from the consumer credit he obtained. The plaintiff, who is capable of acting as a competent individual until the bank's payment demand, evades fulfilling the obligation by claiming incapacity when prompted, exemplifies a clear case of abuse of right. The second constraint imposed on the stipulations of Article 15 of the TMK for completely disabled individuals is articulated in Article 54 of the TCC. As to the aforementioned legal clause, "If equity necessitates, the judge shall impose a sentence on the individual lacking discretionary power to compensate wholly or partially for the damage inflicted." Per Article 54/1 of the TCC, applicable in instances of non-conformity as referenced in Article 98/2 of the TCC, a wholly disabled individual may be held accountable for damages resulting from the other party's reliance on the legitimacy of the defective legal transaction, provided that equity allows. Conversely, Article 452/2 of the TMK states that "if the individual under guardianship deceives the other party concerning his/her capacity to act, he/she shall be liable for the resulting damages." Consequently, it must be acknowledged that an incompetent individual who falsely represents themselves as competent

and engages in a legal transaction, so inflicting harm on the other party, will be accountable for such damage²⁰.

CONCLUSION

The Turkish Civil Code stipulates that individuals with limited capacity cannot engage in any transactions that incur debt without the approval of their legal representative. While the transaction that indebted the legally incompetent individual requires the approval of the legal representative, I contend that such consent will be invalid for any debt transaction resulting in significant asset loss. The legislature has also barred some transactions involving individuals with limited capacity. As previously stated, our legislation unequivocally prohibits transactions such as substantial donations or the founding of foundations. The transactions of those who are utterly disabled are entirely null and invalid. Furthermore, an individual without the capacity for discernment cannot be deemed accountable for their actions. Upon reviewing the Court of Cassation judgment referenced in my research as an exception, it is stated that well-intentioned third parties are afforded protection under our law and will be held liable for torts resulting from total incapacity. Another topic of discussion in the theory is invalidity or cancelability. Proponents of the classical perspective assert that actions undertaken by individuals deemed entirely incompetent are inherently illegitimate and void from inception, but advocates of the contemporary perspective contend that such actions are revocable based on the transaction's dependability.

RESOURCES

Akipek , Jale /Karaman, Derya: Turkish Civil Law (Introduction Provisions, Personal Law),
Volume I , 10th Edition, Istanbul 2013.

²⁰ Court of Cassation 3rd Civil Chamber 2020/5053 E., 2021/3106 K. "Jurisprudence Text"

AUXILIARY RESOURCES

Ayan, Mehmet / Ayan, Nurşen: Introduction to Civil Law, Adalet Publishing House, B.12
Ankara, 2016.

Ayan, Mehmet/ Ayan, Nurşen: Personal Law, Adalet Publishing House, B.9, Ankara, 2020.

Gural , Saymen , Ferit H./ ELBİR: Turkish Law of Obligations,

Hatemi, Hüseyin / Kalkan Oğuztürk, Burcu: Family Law, Vedat Bookstore, Volume 4,
Istanbul 2014.

Köprülü, Bülent: Civil Law, 1992.

Oğuzman, Kemal / Seliçi , Özer / Oktay Özdemir, Saibe : Law of Persons (Real and Legal
Persons), Volume 11, Filiz Bookstore, Istanbul, 2011.

Öztan, Bilge: Basic Concepts of Civil Law, 24th Edition, Ankara 2006.

Part 2, Istanbul 1960.

Sahin, Mustafa; Switzerland Engagement Capacity of Minors and Persons with Limited
Discernment Power (Limited Incompetent Persons) in Turkish Law within the
Framework of the Amendments Made to the Civil Code (TCC Art. 16/I, 118/II), 2020.

Supreme Court of Appeals 3rd Civil Chamber 2020/5053 E., 2021/3106 K. Text of
Jurisprudence

Velidedeoğlu, Hıfzı Veldet : Turkish Civil Law (Personal Law), Volume I ,

Yücer İpek, Evaluation of TMK Art. 15 within the Framework of Application, Journal of the
Union of Turkish Bar Associations, 2014.